

RECENT ADVANCES IN MARINE COMPOSITES RESEARCH

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ABSTRACT

This presentation provides an overview of research on marine composites and sandwich structures, supported by the Solid Mechanics Program, U.S. Office of Naval Research. It includes introductions to 37 ONR supported papers in ONR sessions at ICCM17, in the areas of Marine Composites, Sandwich Structures, Dynamic Failure and Blast, Nanocomposites for Structural Applications, and Full Field Measurement Methods. It also includes discussions of challenges in the use of composites in marine structures, and new directions of research.